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Compliance, cost minimization & production support for textile industry

Md. Anowar Hossain

Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023

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Profile of Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain

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Keywords

Quality services for textile industry, cost minimization & production support, peace of mankind, international platform

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Table 1, Services for Textile Industry

Specialized Review Service	Cost for Six Months
Textile industry (Dyeing & Finishing Plant) review for compliance and environmental support for government	80000USD
Textile industry (Dyeing & Finishing Plant) review for compliance, cost minimization & production support for industry owners	80000USD
Cost Minimization review of Textile Industries	80000USD
Compliance Review of Textile Industries for international buyer satisfaction	80000USD
Dealing with buyer for negotiation of critical issues of textile industries	80000USD

NB: An additional cost will be added for national & international travel & accommodation

Process for Review

A written application to Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain through e-mail: enr.anowar@yahoo.com

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